

Studies on Biologically Active Heterocycles. Part-VI. Synthesis and Biological Activity of 3,5-Disubstituted-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thiones and Thiophosphate Derivatives

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1,3,4-Oxadiazol-2-thiones show a broad spectrum of biological activities¹⁻³. Organophosphates are widely used for controlling pests^{4,7}.

In continuation of our interest in the chemistry of heterocycles⁸, the benzoyl derivatives (3a-n) and diethylthiophosphates (4a-g), of 3-alkyl/aryl/aralkylaminomethyl-5-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thiones (3a-n) were synthesised with a view to getting more active insecticides and bactericides. The 5-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione (1) was prepared⁸ from 2,4-dichlorobenzoylhydrazine. Compounds 2a-n were prepared⁴ by the reaction of thione (1), formaldehyde (35%) and appropriate alkyl/arylamines in ethanol. The benzoyl derivatives (3a-n) were synthesised by benzylation of 2. The thiophosphates (4a-g) were prepared⁶ by the action of *O,O*-diethylthiophosphoryl chloride on 2 in

presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate in dry acetone (Scheme 1). All the compounds gave satisfactory spectral data (Table 1).

The benzoyl derivatives (3a-n) were screened for their antibacterial activities using agar-plate diffusion technique⁹. For screening, 24 h-old culture of *Bacillus cereus*, *Escherichia coli* and *Bacillus megatarium* QMB 1552 were used as test organisms. The results show that compound 3 was found to be very active against all the organisms whereas 4c, e, f, i and l moderately active.

The thiophosphate derivatives (4a-g) were screened for insecticidal activity against *Drosophila melanogaster*-Maigen by residual film evaporation method¹⁰. The activities were evaluated using solution of the compounds (0.01-0.00001%) in acetone and does dependence studies were carried

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3a-n AND 4a-g

Compd. no.	R'	Yield (%)	M.p. °C	δ
3a	C ₆ H ₅	70	140	5.0 (2H, s), 6.6-8.0 (m, 8 ArH)
b	2-(OCH ₃)C ₆ H ₄	78	117	3.4 (3H, s), 5.2 (2H, s), 6.4-7.6 (m, 7 ArH)
c	4-Cl C ₆ H ₄	79	171	5.2 (2H, s), 6.3-7.8 (m, 7 ArH)
d	3-Cl C ₆ H ₄	76	168	5.0 (2H, s), 6.6-8.0 (m, 7 ArH)
e	4-(OCH ₃)C ₆ H ₄	74	131	3.5 (3H, s), 5.2 (2H, s), 6.4-7.8 (m, 7 ArH)
f	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	70	162	1.7 (3H, s), 5.2 (2H, s), 6.4-7.8 (m, 7 ArH)
g	2-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	79	170	1.9 (3H, s), 5.2 (2H, s), 6.5-7.8 (m, 7 ArH)
h	CH ₂ C ₆ H ₅	68	175	4.0 (2H, s), 5.0 (2H, s), 6.8-7.7 (m, 8 ArH)
i	4-(NO ₂)C ₆ H ₄	72	194	5.1 (2H, s), 6.8-8.0 (m, 7 ArH)
j	2-Cl C ₆ H ₄	78	198	5.6 (2H, s), 7.0-8.1 (m, 7 ArH)
k	3-(NO ₂)C ₆ H ₄	74	145	5.3 (2H, s), 6.7-8.0 (m, 7 ArH)
l	2-(NO ₂)C ₆ H ₄	68	185	5.3 (2H, s), 7.4-8.1 (m, 7 ArH)
m	2,4-(Cl) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	81	133	4.6 (2H, s), 6.9-7.7 (m, 6 ArH)
n	CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃	65	138	0.7 (3H, t, J 7Hz), 1.4 (2H, q, J 7Hz), 2.8 (2H, q, J 7Hz), 5.2 (2H, s), 6.8-7.7 (m, 3 ArH)
4a	C ₆ H ₅	45	Gummy	1.5 (6H, t, J 7Hz), 4.3 (4H, dq, J 7Hz), 5.2 (2H, s), 6.8-7.8 (m, 8 ArH)
b	2-(OCH ₃)C ₆ H ₄	40	Gummy	1.5 (6H, t, J 7Hz), 4.3 (4H, dq, J 7Hz), 5.4 (2H, s), 6.9-7.9 (m, 7 ArH)
c	4-Cl C ₆ H ₄	48	Gummy	1.4 (6H, t, J 7Hz), 4.4 (4H, dq, J 7Hz), 5.3 (2H, s), 6.6-8.1 (m, 7 ArH)
d	3-Cl C ₆ H ₄	49	Gummy	1.4 (6H, t, J 7Hz), 4.3 (4H, dq, J 7Hz), 5.6 (2H, s), 6.9-8.0 (m, 7 ArH)
e	4-(OCH ₃)C ₆ H ₄	45	Gummy	1.5 (6H, t, J 7Hz), 4.4 (4H, dq, J 7Hz), 5.4 (2H, s), 6.8-7.6 (m, 7 ArH)
f	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	48	Gummy	1.5 (6H, t, J 7Hz), 4.3 (4H, dq, J 7Hz), 5.4 (2H, s), 6.9-7.9 (m, 7 ArH)
g	2-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	42	Gummy	1.5 (6H, t, J 7Hz), 4.5 (4H, dq, J 7Hz), 5.2 (2H, s), 6.9-7.9 (m, 7 ArH)

out. For the most promising compounds the median lethal concentration values (LC_{50}) were established using probit analysis¹¹. The results show that all the compounds are active.

Scheme 1. Reagents: (i) CH_2O , $R'NH_2$, Δ .

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries on a Büchi oil-heated apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 237B spectrophotometer and pmr spectra ($DMSO-d_6$) on a Varian T-60 spectrometer (60 Hz) using TMS as internal reference.

Preparation of 2a-n. General method: An ethanolic solution of 1 (0.01 mol) formaldehyde (1.5 ml; 35%) and the appropriate amine (0.01 mol) was stirred for 1 h and left overnight in a refrigerator. The solid obtained was washed with cold ethanol and dried.

Preparation of 3a-n. General method: These were prepared by benzoylation of 2 by the Schotten-Bauman method. All the *N*-benzoyl derivatives showed ir absorption bands at 1705–1720, 1660–1610 and 1365–1380 cm^{-1} .

***O,O*-Diethylthiophosphate of 3-substituted-amino-methyl-5-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thiones (4a-g). General method:** To a mixture of 2 (0.01 mol) in dry acetone (50 ml) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (1.38 g, 0.01 mol), was added dropwise *O,O*-diethylthiophosphoryl chloride (DETC; 1.88 g, 0.01 mol). The mixture was then refluxed for 6–7 h till the reaction was complete (tlc). Solvent was then removed and the residue chromatographed over a column of silica gel using benzene as an eluent. The thiophosphate derivatives (4a-g) were obtained as viscous substance after removing the solvent. The diethylthiophosphates showed a typical absorption band at 750–780 cm^{-1} .

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